

POST-FIRE RESIDUAL STRESS PREDICTIONS IN STEEL I-SECTIONS

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ABSTRACT

Fire has been recognized as a significant cause of structural failures in recent decades, and increasingly sophisticated experimental and analytical tools are being developed to better predict the responses of structures to natural fires. Structures are also known to collapse several hours after the fires were extinguished, indicating that although they survived the fire, they could not withstand the post-fire stresses. These post-fire stresses may arise due to system behavioural changes that happen in the cooling phase of a fire or due to additional locked-in stresses due to the rapid heating and cooling of structural members. Residual stresses play a primary role in the design strength equations of steel beams and columns, even at ambient temperatures. However, there needs to be more understanding of how the distribution and magnitude of these residual stresses change after the event of a fire and its impact on the residual strength of structures. Limited data in the literature indicate a reduction in the residual stresses after exposure to high temperatures, but the studies were limited to all-side exposure (uniform temperature) and natural air cooling. The present work uses finite element simulations to predict the residual stresses in compact steel I-sections for both air and water cooling after the event of a fire.

Keywords: Residual strength, Residual stresses, Finite Element Modelling, Fire exposure, ABAQUS

1 INTRODUCTION

Structural failure due to fires has become more common in recent decades. Some incidents, such as the collapse of the Plasco building (1), a 17-storey structure in Iran, and the Windsor Tower (2) in Spain, are examples of severe fire damage in multi-storied steel structures. Another incident in the Broadgate development in London, UK (3), witnessed a severe fire during construction but saw no significant deformations, highlighting the potential redundancy and strength of steel structures. In studying cases such as the Windsor Tower, where the fire spread through different storeys, and in the Broadgate development, where the members suffered no visible damage (potentially leading to re-use of the members), it is interesting to question the mechanical properties and stresses locked-in the steel members after their cooling. Further, the nature of these post-fire stresses depends on the rate at which the structure cools down from the elevated temperature. Typically, fire-exposed steel members are cooled using air-cooling or water-cooling. While air-cooling is gradual, water-cooling is relatively faster, with a greater potential to produce a larger magnitude of residual stress. Hence, the magnitude and distribution of the post-fire residual stresses vary widely between these two cooling methods. Subsequently, the changes caused in the residual stresses during the cooling phase can influence the residual strength of the structural members. It is, therefore, essential to measure the post-fire residual stresses to assess the capacity of fire-exposed structural steel members.

Wang and Lui (4) investigate the pre- and post-fire residual stresses in Q690 welded I-sections. They examined the effects of temperature exposure, cooling methods, heating rate, and flange width-to-thickness ratio on residual stresses. Their findings showed that the exposure temperature significantly influences the residual stresses, while the flange width-to-thickness ratio has minimal impact on their

distribution. Considerable residual stresses form at flange edges and at the web-flange junctions when temperature exposure exceeds 700 °C and when cooled by water quenching.

Although there are proven experimental methods to measure residual stresses, such as sectioning, hole drilling, blind hole drilling, and x-ray diffraction, they are typically time-consuming and require substantial financial resources. The current study performs numerical simulations to predict the residual stresses of hot-rolled steel I-sections after cooling to ambient conditions when subjected to elevated temperatures and cooled using air or water. The cooling in water is expected to simulate an extremely quick rate of cooling. The post-fire residual stress predictions are made using finite element (FE) simulations in ABAQUS (5). However, the scope of this paper is limited to wide-flange hot-rolled I-sections. The results of these studies suggest the merits and demerits of one cooling method over the other by accounting for its effect on the residual stresses.

2 FINITE ELEMENT MODELLING

This section elaborates on the type of analysis conducted, the geometry of the cross-sections, boundary conditions, and the material parameters involved.

2.1 Geometry and boundary conditions

The numerical analysis is performed on a hot-rolled wide-flange section (W920 x 223), whose measured residual stresses are available in Huber's experimental study (6). The dimensions of the section are shown in *Fig. 1*. The length of the I-beam is 2.7 m, which is approximately three times the depth of the cross-section, as adapted by Huber (6). The FE model uses an eight-node thermally coupled brick element (C3D8T) with trilinear displacement and temperature capabilities. A mesh convergence study determined an optimum mesh size of 10 mm in both flanges and the web. The ends of the I-girder are modelled as torsionally and flexurally simply-supported.

Fig. 1. I-beam cross-sectional dimensions and finite element mesh for residual stress analysis

2.2 Material properties

The mechanical and thermal properties are defined in the material module. The thermal properties of steel, such as thermal conductivity, specific heat, and heat transfer coefficients and mechanical properties, such as Young's modulus of elasticity, Poisson's ratio, and the thermal expansion coefficient, are functions of temperature. *Fig. 2* shows the variations of mechanical and thermal properties with temperature used in the numerical modelling. The steel yield strength (f_y) used in the

model is 350 MPa. The stress-plastic strain curves for different temperatures are incorporated through the multilinear kinematic hardening model shown in *Fig. 3*.

Fig. 2. Mechanical and thermal properties of structural steel as functions of temperature: (a) Young's Modulus of elasticity (7); (b) Poisson's ratio (8); (c) Thermal conductivity (9); (d) Specific heat (9); (e) combined heat transfer coefficient (7); (f) Thermal expansion (10).

The interaction module defines the heating and cooling processes. For the heating phase, a constant convective heat transfer coefficient of 25 W/(m²K) and a surface radiation emissivity of 0.8 recommended by Eurocode (9), are considered. During the air cooling phase, this study adopts a combined temperature-dependent heat transfer model suggested by Brickstad and Josefson (7). The heat transfer coefficient used for air cooling, accounting for both convection and radiation is shown in *Fig. 2(f)*. However, sensitivity analysis finds a constant convection heat transfer coefficient of

10,000 W/(m²K) suitable for water cooling, which falls within the general range of 100-20,000 W/(m²K) as recommended by Incropera et al.(11).

Fig. 3. Multilinear kinematic stress (σ_x) vs plastic strain (ϵ_x) hardening model adapted from Stoddard and Yarnold (12)

2.3 A description of the FE analyses

Eight numerical simulations are run to capture the residual stresses in the hot-rolled sections when they are subjected to different target temperatures and cooled by exposure to air and water. Four models are cooled using air, and the remaining four specimens are cooled by water. The simulations are carried out in the following three steps.

1. The specimen is subjected to an initial temperature of 1300 °C to mimic the manufacturing process of the hot-rolled section. Subsequently, residual stresses due to the hot-rolling process are measured using the air cooling parameters discussed in Section 2.2. This represents the initial state of the specimen before subjecting it to fire.

Fig. 4. ISO 834 heating to target temperature and followed by cooling in air/cooling in water on hot-rolled specimens

2. The hot-rolled specimens are then subjected to target temperatures of 300 °C, 600 °C, 750 °C, and 900°C at heating rates specified by the ISO 834 standard temperature-time curve (13). The residual stresses measured in the first step are given as the input to the specimen at the beginning of the heating phase. The target temperature is maintained constant for 60 minutes to ensure a uniform temperature distribution in the specimen. The heating phase as per ISO 834 standard temperature-time curve and cooling phases involving air and water are illustrated in *Fig. 4*.
3. The residual stresses of the air-cooled and water-cooled hot-rolled specimens are finally measured.

Temperatures as high as 900°C are included in these studies for two reasons: 1. It is possible that in fires during construction, the members, on account of being subjected to insignificant loads, may withstand higher temperatures, and the residual mechanical properties and stresses would be of interest. 2. These studies also serve as benchmark studies for our future studies with composite construction, such as CFST columns and other insulated steel members.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This section presents the results of the residual stresses for the hot-rolled section when cooled from different elevated temperatures listed in Section 2.3. *Fig. 5* shows the residual stresses of the hot-rolled specimen and Huber's (6) experiment data. *Figs. 6(a)* and *(b)* show the residual stresses of the I-section after air and water cooling, respectively. The black lines in both figures indicate the residual stresses present due to the manufacturing process (obtained using the procedure outlined in step 1 of Section 2.3). The following observations are made from *Fig. 6*.

1. The initial residual stresses formed from the manufacturing process are typical of a hot-rolled I-section. Tensile residual stresses are formed at the web-flange junctions, and compressive residual stresses are formed at the flange tips and in the middle of the web. These observations are consistent with the findings by Huber (6), Alpsten (14) and Quayyum and Hassan (15).
2. The peak residual stresses for the hot-rolled section at the web-flange junctions and flange tips are 99 MPa (tension) and 69 MPa (compression), respectively, while in the middle of the web, the residual stress is 40 MPa (compression). Similarly, Huber's experimental peak residual stress for the web-flange junctions and flange tips are 101.76 MPa (tension) and 69 MPa (compression) after hot-rolling. The predicted numerical results agree well with the experimental work shown in *Fig. 5*. The residual stress from numerical modelling is the average value of residual stresses through the flanges and web thickness.

Fig. 5. Residual stress of W920 x 223 hot-rolled sections

3. Fig. 6(a) reveals that an increase in exposure temperature corresponds to a reduction in residual stresses when the specimens are cooled in air. When the specimen is cooled from 300 °C, the peak compressive and tensile residual stresses in the flanges is 60 MPa, while the peak compressive residual stress is 41 MPa in the middle of the web. The flange residual stresses reduce by 33% in tension and 40% in compression, compared to the initial residual stresses due to the hot-rolling process. However, there is little variation in the web residual stresses compared to the initial residual stresses of hot-rolled sections.

Fig. 6. Residual stress distribution in the top and bottom flanges and the web

4. The tensile and compressive residual stresses in the flanges as well as the web are similar in both cooling methods when cooled from 300 °C. Therefore, cooling methods do not affect the residual stresses up to exposure temperatures of 300 °C.
5. When the section is exposed to a temperature of 600 °C and cooled by air, the web-flange junction stress reduce to 28 MPa (tension) and to 24 MPa (compression) at the flange edge. However, in the water-cooled specimens, the peak residual stress at the web flange junction increases to 120 MPa (tension) and to 220 MPa (compression) at the flange edges. An increase in the residual stresses is observed for the water-cooled specimen. In contrast, the residual stress decreases in the air-cooled specimen at the web-flange junctions and flange edges compared to the unheated hot rolled sections. The residual stresses at the web centre decrease, and the web edges increase compared to the unheated hot-rolled sections in water cooling methods.
6. When the hot-rolled sections are exposed to over 750 °C, and quenched by water, noticeable residual stresses are formed at the web-flange junctions, flange edges, middle of the web, and web edges. These stresses result from a sudden drop in the temperature of the specimen due to water-cooling, wherein there is no sufficient time for the stress relaxation to happen.
7. When the section is exposed to a temperature of 750 °C, the residual stress in the web-flange junction for air-cooled specimens is 4 MPa, and 180 MPa for water-cooled specimens. A similar trend in the residual stress values is observed for both air and water-cooled specimens at 900 °C. So, water cooling impacts the residual stresses more than air cooling, especially beyond the steel eutectoid temperature of 750 °C. The residual stresses at the web-flange junctions, at the flange tips and in the middle of the webs are listed in *Table 1*.

The results from these studies suggest that water cooling substantially impacts the post-fire residual stresses, leading to a significant increase in residual stresses at higher temperatures. The difference in behaviour between air- and water-cooling methods highlights the importance of understanding the residual strengths of members after different cooling methods.

Table 1. The residual stresses in the flanges and web of fire-exposed cooled specimens

	Cooling methods	Web flange junctions (MPa)	Flange edges (MPa)	Web centre (MPa)	Web edges (MPa)
Hot-rolled sections		90.2	-69.0	-40.4	54.5
300 °C	CIA	60.9	-46.3	-41.6	56.2
	CIW	66.3	-50.3	-41.6	56.2
600 °C	CIA	28.0	-23.8	-19.5	31.9
	CIW	120.9	-220.2	-29.8	156.2
750 °C	CIA	4.9	-16.3	0.9	8.0
	CIW	178.5	-229.5	-81.8	145.5
900 °C	CIA	3.5	-11.8	0.7	5.9
	CIW	183.0	-236.0	-142.1	140.8

CIA – Cooling in Air; CIW – Cooling in Water: positive indicates tension; negative indicates compression

4 CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents valuable insights into the residual stresses of hot-rolled steel I-sections subjected to different elevated temperatures and cooling methods.

1. The elevated temperatures and different cooling methods influence the magnitude and distribution of residual stresses in hot-rolled sections.

2. When cooled from 300 °C, the peak tensile and compressive residual stresses in the flanges and web are the same in both cooling methods. However, when the temperature is increased beyond 600 °C, air cooling (a gradual cooling process) and water-cooling (rapid cooling) impact the magnitude and distribution of residual stresses differently.
3. The air-cooled residual stresses are reduced when the temperature exposure is greater than 600 °C. When the temperature exceeds 750 °C, the residual stresses are negligible in the air-cooled sections.
4. When the exposed temperature exceeds 600 °C, the water-cooled residual stresses drastically increase compared to unexposed hot-rolled sections, suggesting a lower residual strength of water-cooled steel I-sections.

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